

Unveiling Female Confidence: The Influence of the Makeover Trope in 2000-2010 Chick Flicks on Adolescent Perceptions

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of the makeover trope in popular American chick flicks from 2000-2010 on the perceptions of female confidence among adolescents aged 14-18. The makeover trope, characterized by transformative narratives centered around physical and emotional elements, has been a staple in films targeting young female audiences; however, its possibly negative effects on shaping perceptions of female confidence remain unexplored. A mixed-methods approach was employed, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative analyses. Five top-grossing chick flicks from 2000-2010 were selected for content analysis, focusing on the frequency of positive and negative representations of the makeover trope in each film. For a quantitative approach, pre and post-experimental surveys were administered to female adolescents, assessing their beliefs regarding female confidence and the makeover trope's influence. The content analysis revealed a majority of negative representations of the makeover trope in the selected films, indicating potential detrimental impacts on young audiences. However, statistical analysis of survey responses did not yield significant differences in perceptions of female confidence between control and experimental groups exposed to clips displaying the makeover trope. While the statistical findings suggest no direct influence of the makeover trope on perceptions of female confidence, qualitative insights indicate a nuanced relationship. These findings underscore the importance of evaluating media portrayals and suggest a need for healthier representations of female confidence in teen-targeted films.

Keywords: *female confidence, adolescent, content analysis, social science, makeover trope, female adolescent*

1. INTRODUCTION

The makeover trope, though uncommonly mentioned, is frequent in multiple forms of cinema targeted toward women, from *Cinderella* for children to *Mean Girls* for adolescents. This trope is defined to have a transformative narrative, where the characters go “from mundane to beautiful,” physically or mentally, as a response to how other characters view them (TV Tropes, 2020). Most films that utilize this literary technique display a similar, stereotypical plotline: the protagonist is initially perceived negatively due to specific aspects of their identity (primarily attractiveness and personality) and dedicates the rest of the film attempting to fix this issue – often to please other characters, which the protagonist believes would consequently please themselves.

Along with the toxic nature of the trope itself, many of the clichés formed by the makeover trope have paralleled gender stereotypes for as far back as the 1940s, specifically dominating themes of physical beauty and submissive nature (Kumar, et al., 2022). The behaviors shown in films presenting the makeover trope encourage their viewers to alter their physical looks (at times, for sexual purposes) and personas as a way to empower themselves and their confidence levels (Marston, 2010). These detrimental portrayals of women have had minimal change over the years, remaining continuous in the 21st Century, and appear prominently in the film genre of chick flicks, which are described as films that feature female protagonists and target a young female audience (O’Neil, 2016). Although chick flicks rose to fame in the late 1990s, they were most popular in the early 2000s to 2010s, suggesting that the makeover trope was also prevalent at this time (Barker, 2015). In regards to the destructive themes the makeover trope introduces to young female audiences through these films, this research will explore makeover culture in chick flicks and answer the question: How does the “makeover trope” in popular American chick flicks from 2000-2010 influence the perceptions of females aged 14-18 on the portrayal of female confidence?

The majority of research conducted on the makeover trope in relation to female adolescent viewers focused primarily on topics concerning feminism and gender inequality in films (and other forms of media) displaying the makeover trope. Very few sources of research delved into both the makeover trope and the film genre of chick flicks simultaneously and mostly pinpointed one element or the other. Due to the introduction of chick flicks during the postfeminist era, there were frequent works studying a selected number of films from the late

1990s to the early 2000s, but few to almost none researched within the 2000 to 2010 time period. This is an essential decade because it takes place directly after the postfeminism era, highlighting the extended impacts that the postfeminism era had on film targeted toward women. The key element, however, that differentiates this research from others, is the attention on the audience's perception of female confidence; a number of sources discuss the stereotypes behind the strong, confident female protagonists, but do not explore the impacts it may have on the young viewers, specifically adolescents. Additionally, it can be assumed that the adolescent ages focused on in this research, 14-18, is the most impressionable age group. These gaps can be approached by connecting all three elements – the makeover trope, the chick flick genre, and the concept of female confidence – into both an experimental study and content analysis, covering all aspects of the research thesis. In conducting this study, it can be hypothesized that the makeover trope found in popular American chick flicks from the allotted time period, 2000 to 2010, will negatively influence the perceptions of the female adolescent audience sample. These results may propose that the film industry will alter the destructive stereotypes portrayed within the makeover trope and produce adolescent-targeted films that will display positive themes of confidence.

Literature Review

Portrayals of Toxicity in Makeover Chick Flicks

As shown through the fields of observational psychology, young audiences tend to learn coping behaviors from the characters they view on-screen (Shelton, 2023). This concept holds significance to the content that is shown in chick flicks featuring the makeover trope, as there are often harmful themes illustrated in seemingly common films surrounding female confidence and empowerment, which the viewers then consume and mimic.

In an exploratory study, Behm-Morawitz and Mastro conducted an experiment to determine how gender portrayals in teen movies influence the viewers' perceptions of women based on the featured female characters and circumstances. Most of the films that were analyzed represented themes of social aggressiveness from female characters and the audience primarily associated female friendships in these films with negative stereotypes (Behm-Morawitz & Mastro, 2008). Due to how the adolescent viewers perceived the relationships between women in the films, it can be suggested that they believe this is how they should behave within their own

friendships, guiding them to destructive paths that may hurt the individuals they are associating with and themselves. One of the most popular chick flicks of the 21st Century, *Mean Girls* (2004), emphasizes this idea by highlighting that their female adolescent audience has engaged in the film's practices for decades. The plot of this film surrounds the ideals of toxic femininity in society and several instances of bullying. However, many of the characters' behaviors are seen to be embedded in popular culture, encouraging young girls to imitate them; this is showcased in the online videos and trends created by viewers teaching others how to recreate the "Burn Book" from *Mean Girls*, which is a book in the film made specifically for ridiculing other women (Colling, 2014). Creator Tina Fey notes that she readapted *Mean Girls* in 2024 as a result of the success of the original movie, which presents a problem because instead of altering these damaging portrayals of female empowerment, the film industry is recreating popular chick flicks and contributing to the unfavorable recurrences of the makeover trope towards young women (CBS News, 2024).

The Role of the Makeover Trope on Teen Girls' Confidence

While the portrayals of destructive plotlines in films have a significant influence on their female adolescent audience, they can also specifically impact the viewers' perception of female confidence. The majority of films in the postfeminist era with a female protagonist focus on themes of female empowerment, but often fail to display positive reinforcements of empowerment as a result of the repetitive storylines revolving around the makeover trope (Ivey, 2017). As showcased in *The Princess Diaries* (2001), the protagonist is originally deemed unattractive, with features such as bushy eyebrows, glasses, and curly hair; she is then given a physical makeover to make her seem more feminine-like and becomes more confident in herself after her transformation. From the plot of this film, it is evident that the authors purposely highlighted societal beauty standards as a way to display female confidence. There is a notion present that it was necessary for the protagonist to alter her appearance to feel more confident, which emphasizes this ideology to the young audiences watching *The Princess Diaries*. In an experimental study conducted by Maillim Santiago, the researcher advanced the idea that young female audiences consume the toxic portrayals of media that parallel societal standards and they reflect it upon themselves (Santiago, 2013). The viewers who watch these representations of women and believe that they are accurate portrayals of female confidence may attempt to fit the

standards that they are shown. At times, this desire to align with the societal beauty standards that are glamorized on-screen can lead to extreme circumstances. Makeover culture in films can gradually lead to the route of cosmetic surgery for young women who have been consistently exposed to the unhealthy portrayals of pushing society's beauty standards toward women (Jones, 2006). This all contributes to the narrow focus, recognizing the makeover trope as a damaging literary device in films that are targeted toward young girls.

2. Methodology

This study was proposed to determine if the makeover trope influences female adolescents' perceptions of female confidence; particularly when the trope is utilized in the Chick Flick film genre. In order to evaluate the predicted hypothesis, a mixed-methodology approach would be the most suitable, as it allows for both qualitative and quantitative data collection. Narrowing in on the qualitative data collection, a content analysis would be necessary to thoroughly explore the positive and negative depictions regarding female confidence in a selected number of Chick Flicks that were released within the time period of 2000-2010. Five Chick Flicks were selected: *Legally Blonde* (2001), *The Princess Diaries* (2001), *Mean Girls* (2004), *Wild Child* (2008), and *Easy A* (2010) – all of which were top-grossing American films of 2000-2010 and utilized the makeover trope (Nash Information Services, LLC, 2024). The films were to be fully viewed and analyzed on the positive and negative representations of the makeover trope. In regards to the quantitative data collection, an experimental method needed to be conducted to manipulate “female confidence” as a variable. A pre-experimental survey was sent out to female adolescents aged 14-18 through a multitude of social media platforms (Instagram, Discord, and Reddit) as well as educational platforms (Jupiter Ed); those who chose to complete the survey would then move on to the post-experimental survey. The pre-survey assisted in understanding the participants' personal beliefs on specific aspects of the makeover trope and female confidence, while the post-survey directed participants to watch brief clips from the featured Chick Flicks from the content analysis and answer questions. The two separate forms were used as a measuring technique to determine if there was any direct impact from the Chick Flick clips shown on the participants' beliefs regarding female confidence. In the post-experimental survey, participants were randomly assigned to be in the control group or the experimental group: the control group participants viewed clips from the selected Chick Flicks

with plotlines revolving around female confidence (*Legally Blonde* and *Mean Girls*), while the experimental group participants viewed clips from the Chick Flicks with plotlines that were not dependent on female confidence as an element (*Wild Child* and *Easy A*). Both the control and experimental group participants viewed a shared clip from *The Princess Diaries*, which was neutral to the theme of female confidence. The experimental method was the most appropriate choice for this study because it enables “female confidence” to be manipulated in the context of the makeover trope within films and allows for the data to contain firsthand responses from the participants. Furthermore, the mixed-methods approach was especially significant because the primary quantitative data from the participants could not be collected accurately without the qualitative data via the content analysis being thoroughly evaluated.

Materials

Before forming the data collection techniques of this study, it was imperative to determine which Chick Flicks to examine for the content analysis. A resource that was utilized was a box office record from Nash Information Services, LLC., which documented all the top-grossing romantic comedies of all time (Nash Information Services, LLC, 2024). Searching for films that were top-grossing was essential because it would suggest that those were the most popular Chick Flicks of their time, since they were prominently viewed, and can lead to the assumption that they may be the most influential films to their audiences. In regard to the content analysis, a tool of measurement was necessary to assess the representations of the makeover trope in the selected films, so a content analysis coding process that targeted the frequencies of particular behaviors was chosen. Those frequencies were then logged on a Google Spreadsheet for organization purposes concerning the data analysis. For the quantitative data collection, Google Forms was utilized for both the pre-experimental and post-experimental surveys as a means to receive and review participant information in an orderly manner as well as have an efficient way to spread the study to individuals who qualified to participate. The engine also allowed the study to expand the types of survey questions with open-ended, multiple choice, and linear scale options, which encouraged for a more diverse scale of thematic elements to explore in the surveys and did not limit the study to only utilize the element of the makeover trope.

Qualitative Data Through a Content Analysis

In this study, a qualitative content analysis is ideal because it allows for an in-depth examination of certain behaviors regarding the makeover trope shown in Chick Flicks. Each of the selected films – *Legally Blonde*, *The Princess Diaries*, *Mean Girls (2004)*, *Wild Child*, and *Easy A* – were observed and analyzed for positive and negative behaviors of the makeover trope and “positive behaviors” and “negative behaviors” were defined for the specific context. Positive behaviors regarding the makeover trope would be indications that the character undergoing the makeover transformation was improving in their previous behavior patterns and finding a breakthrough within themselves. Negative behaviors regarding the makeover trope would be the opposite, where the character undergoing the transformation was worsening in terms of behavior and had little to no signs of reflection within themselves. In order to evaluate the significance of these behaviors, a code was used where the frequencies of each behavior were monitored. This coding system was modeled from a study by Nermina Durmic where she analyzed the project success rate of Information Technology projects by coding five specific project success factors and how frequently they appeared in a selected number of projects (Durmic, 2020). It is essential to monitor the frequencies of both positive and negative behaviors to determine if the makeover trope has primarily a positive or negative influence on its young viewers. In this study, the following code was used for each of the selected films:

Category	Code	Frequency per Code
The Makeover Trope	1. Positive Behavior	TBD
	2. Negative Behavior	TBD

Quantitative Data via an Experimental Approach

The qualitative data collection acts as a segue into the quantitative data collection, which is most valuable to the purpose of this study: the makeover trope’s effect on the samples’ perceptions of female confidence. In this specific approach, the element of “female confidence” is being manipulated as a dependent variable to the participants in the post-experimental survey while the particular film that is being presented is manipulated as an independent variable. In the pre-experimental survey, there were open-ended questions, multiple choice questions, as well as linear scale questions, but all of the questions on the form were only in regard to the participants’

personal experiences and opinions of the makeover trope and female confidence (See Appendix A for some of the questions that were asked in the pre-experimental survey.) The open-ended questions were incorporated into the survey to target participants' in-depth understanding of their personal beliefs regarding female confidence; since the answer is entirely up to them, they are able to grasp what certain terms and scenarios may signify to them in their own words. By understanding the participants' personal beliefs and experiences with the makeover trope and female confidence through the pre-experimental survey, there is a baseline for the post-experimental survey; it acts as a tool of measurement for the makeover trope's influence.

In the post-experimental survey, the questions were targeted to assess the participants' understanding of the clips and to measure if their opinions had changed regarding some of the aspects of female confidence from the clips they had seen. Each clip specifically aimed to show the character undergoing the makeover trope, whether it was the makeover scene itself, or two clips of the protagonist before and after the transformation. This allowed for the makeover trope to be a constant variable, regardless of the prominent presence of female confidence in the selected films' plotlines (See Appendix B for some of the questions that were asked in the post-experimental survey after the participants viewed the featured clips from the selection of Chick Flicks.) Although the participants in the control group viewed separate clips from those in the experimental group, all the questions asked in the survey were tackling direct instances of the makeover that the featured film's protagonist underwent. There were some variations of these questions that targeted additional elements, such as societal female stereotypes and scenarios where the participant must make decisions relating to the content they viewed previously. It is significant for these additional elements to be present in the survey questions, as they encourage the participants to consider the real-life applications of the makeover trope and the dramatic consequences it may have on young audiences, such as themselves. Regardless of secondary themes, all the questions in the post-experimental survey focused explicitly on the aspect of female confidence that was shown in the film clips.

3. Results and Analysis

As mentioned, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected to prompt the results of this research. The qualitative data collection consisted of a content analysis from the coding frequency system, calculating how often specific representations and themes are presented in the

selected chick flicks. It was found that there were more frequencies of negative representations of the makeover trope in the majority of the selected films than there were positive representations, displaying that young adolescent audiences are prone to more negative exposure in chick flicks rather than positive. In the content analysis, each selected film (*Legally Blonde*, *The Princess Diaries*, *Mean Girls* [2004], *Wild Child*, and *Easy A*) were applied to the coding frequency system where “positive behavior” and “negative behavior” were observed as codes and were defined prior, in terms of what specific character attitudes were being noted for. Each scene that was observed to fall within one of the codes in the frequency system was recorded for each movie. From the qualitative data, the content analysis concluded that three out of five of the films — *The Princess Diaries*, *Mean Girls*, and *Easy A* —were more frequent in negative behaviors regarding the makeover trope than positive behaviors, with *Mean Girls* peaking at 19 instances of negative behavior and *Legally Blonde* at 13 instances of positive behavior. The results from the coding frequency system are shown in the table below:

Category: The Makeover Trope	Code	Frequency per Code
<i>Legally Blonde</i>	1. Positive Behavior	13
	2. Negative Behavior	1
<i>The Princess Diaries</i>	1. Positive Behavior	4
	2. Negative Behavior	10
<i>Mean Girls</i> (2004)	1. Positive Behavior	3
	2. Negative Behavior	19
<i>Wild Child</i>	1. Positive Behavior	8
	2. Negative Behavior	5
<i>Easy A</i>	1. Positive Behavior	2
	2. Negative Behavior	11

Regarding the qualitative and quantitative data collected from the pre-experimental and post-experimental surveys, a thematic analysis and statistical analysis were conducted. In the post-experimental surveys, both the control group and experimental group were given primarily open-ended questions and the pre-experimental survey contained a few questions of that style as well. Open-ended questions allowed the participants to generate personal, unique responses that cannot be grouped as numerical data can, so it was practical to conduct a thematic analysis (Cho, 2014). The pre-experimental survey served as an understanding of the participants’ perceptions of female confidence and the makeover trope as general terms. All of the responses from the open-ended questions from the pre-experimental survey were grouped together to identify response themes and two significant themes emerged, as shown below:

- *Describe what you think a confident female character should be like in terms of behavior.*
 True to themself/Unafraid to speak up - 43%
 Kind and Uplifting - 35%

- *Describe what you think a confident female character should be like in terms of looks.*
 There should not be a specific look for confident females - 48%
 Sophisticated/“Knows how to carry themself” - 34%

While the majority of the survey questions were open-ended and required a qualitative analysis approach, there were also quantitative results available from the post-experimental surveys from both the control and experimental group using linear scale questions. A Student’s t-test (or simply, t-test) was utilized to “measure the means of two groups” (Hayes, 2023). For this study, specifically the means of the experimental group and the control group are being calculated and compared, so the t-test for independent samples had to be administered using the formula below:

$$t = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_p^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_p^2}{n_2}}}$$

Breakdown:

The numerator is the difference between the two sample means: \bar{x}_1 is the mean value of sample 1 and \bar{x}_2 is of sample 2.

The denominator is the formula for the standard error: s being the standard deviation, n being the number of cases, and p being the p-value [which “tells us how likely it is that we would draw a sample that deviates from the population by the same amount or more than a sample we drew” (DATAtab, 2023).]; the numbers in the formula correspond with the sample that the data is being taken from (sample 1 or 2).

This formula will determine if the mean values in both independent groups are the same, otherwise known as the null hypothesis, or if the mean values in the groups are unequal, also known as the alternative hypothesis. For this study, the alternative hypothesis that is being tested is whether the means in survey responses for the control group and experimental group participants are unequal, which would indicate that the makeover trope in the chick flick film clips that they were asked to watch did have an influence on their perception of female confidence. While both post-experimental surveys had different questions regarding separate chick flicks, the final questions on both surveys were in regards to the physical makeover scene in *The Princess Diaries*, which involved the participants to reflect on their own experiences (as well as the topics explored in the previous survey questions) with the makeover trope and how it would impact their confidence level; they are shown below:

- *In this scene, the protagonist, Mia, is given a physical makeover to make her look "more like a princess."*
Put yourself in Mia's shoes: How healthy would it be for you and your self-perception to undergo this makeover?
- *How willing would you be to undergo this makeover?*
(If you were given the opportunity to have this makeover with Paolo and "look like a princess" yourself, would you?)

The responses to these questions were on a linear scale, allowing for the means to be calculated. After both means were calculated from the control and experimental group responses, they were inputted into the formula to receive a t-value of 0.9543. Next, the degrees of freedom (df), which are “the maximum number of logically independent values” in a data set, had to be calculated utilizing the formula below, to get a result of 32:

$$df = n_1 + n_2 - 2$$

Breakdown:

n_1 is the number of participants from the first sample (in this study, experimental group), while n_2 is the number of participants from the second sample (control group).

The final step was to calculate the p-value, which was done through an online calculator for a value of 0.3471. These data points were then translated into a bell curve graph for a better visual understanding of how significantly the sample represents the overall population of female adolescents aged 14-18, as shown below:

The t-test measured a t-value of 0.954, degrees of freedom of 32, and a p-value of 0.347, which is close to 0.

As seen in the graph and the discussed results, the p-value is 0.347, close to 0, highlighting that there is essentially no difference in the means of the control and experimental group and that the utilization of female confidence as a variable did not influence the perceptions of the sample participants.

4. Discussion

The results collected from this research study offer a meaningful discussion concerning the impact of the makeover trope. The findings that were gathered aimed to respond to the research question: How does the “makeover trope” in popular American chick flicks from

2000-2010 influence the perceptions of females aged 14-18 on the portrayal of female confidence? The intended hypothesis was that the makeover trope would influence the sample of female adolescents negatively regarding their perceptions of female confidence, but the findings did not correlate with this thesis. However, there are still notable findings from this study that can assist in future research studies and add to the body of knowledge.

From the content analysis, it is adamant that *Mean Girls* had the most frequent negative representations of the makeover trope; however, in the pre-experimental survey, 44 out of 50 participants (88%) reported that they watched the movie — the highest percentage out of all the films listed, which proposes that the most unhealthy film is also the one with the most exposure to young female audiences. Another noteworthy subject is that the film with the most positive behavior regarding the makeover trope, *Legally Blonde*, was released in 2001, the earliest year of all the selected films. This may suggest that chick flicks' positive and healthy representations of the makeover trope have declined over time. In regards to the thematic analysis, most of the themes identified previously directly come from the participants' perceptions from chick flick films. When responding, many participants began with an introduction that followed the lines of "stereotypically," or "usually, in movies." Furthermore, the multiple choice questions that followed the open-ended questions in the pre-experimental survey asked the participant to answer whether their description of a female character (regarding physical appearance or behavior) correlated with the female protagonists they had seen in any chick flicks. In terms of behavior, 50% of participants (25 out of 50) answered that their response "somewhat" correlated, while for physical appearance, 44% of participants (22 out of 50) responded with "Yes," further indicating that the participants' responses were adjacent to exposure they have experienced to stereotypical confident characters in films. Majority of participants also expressed that they believe characters from chick flicks influence both themselves and societal trends surrounding teens. On a linear scale from 1-10 (1 being the least influence and 10 being the highest) 24 out of 50 participants chose between scales 6-10 when asked if characters from chick flicks influence their behaviors and personal interests. Adding on, 47 participants out of 50 chose between scales 6-10 when asked if characters from chick flicks influence trends for their age group through social media, fashion choices, etc. These data results prove that female teenagers feel as if they are prone to the impacts of chick flicks, which should be studied further.

This study and similar research conducted by other individuals may have discrepancies for numerous reasons. In this study conducted by Madison Ivey, there is only a content analysis, focusing on the analysis of connotations of three chick flicks (Ivey, 2017). The complexity in both variables and methodology of this study can be a viable explanation for differences among research; while other researchers focused primarily on a content analysis for female confidence as a variable, this study conducted a content analysis, experiment, thematic analysis, and statistical analysis of both female confidence and the makeover trope as variables, which were not previously considered together in past studies. A possible limitation in this study was the sample size; 50 participants are only a small percentage of the population of female adolescents aged 14-18. This could also explain why the p-value from the statistical analysis did not reach 0.5 and is deemed insignificantly applicable. Another factor regarding the sample size was the lack of diversity within the participants. Most participants were from New York City and attended the same high school, which can hinder the generalizability of the data results, since it can be assumed that they experience similar environments. Adding on, the surveys used may be more unreliable as predicted. The participants were required to have their name on both the pre-experimental survey and post-experimental survey and although they were told that the identification was simply for progress checking and would remain anonymous outside of the researcher, the participants still may have felt uncomfortable to express their genuine opinions, as the surveys were self-administered. However, this study takes into account the importance of the makeover trope as a variable for adolescent girls, which has been a niche, unexplored topic prior and would be deemed as a fundamental component of future studies.

5. Conclusion

This research study aimed to determine the association between the makeover culture, as featured in the chick flick film genre, and female adolescents' perceptions of female confidence through qualitative and quantitative data analysis. The present findings confirmed that there was no statistically significant relationship between these two variables, as shown with a p-value of less than 0.5 through the performed Student's t-test. Under an experimental approach, surveys were released to the population of female teenagers aged 14-18 and a sample of 50 participants was received. These participants were given a pre-experimental survey to understand their personal beliefs regarding the variables of the study and a post-experimental survey (a separately

made survey for both the control group and experimental group) in order to measure the influence, if any, of the participants' exposure to the chick flicks to their perception of female confidence. While the responses displayed in the pre-experimental survey corresponded with the intended hypothesis, there was no consistent data in the post-experimental surveys that presented a difference between the control group and the experimental group. Qualitative data was also examined through a content analysis of each selected chick flick, demonstrating that there were more frequent negative behaviors regarding the makeover trope found in such films, rather than positive behaviors. Under certain assumptions, the qualitative results can be construed as evidence that the makeover trope does have an influence on female adolescents' perceptions of female confidence. However, there is no statistically sound corroboration from the conducted experiment, ultimately resulting in the final conclusion.

The qualitative data is still noteworthy, but future research should certainly further test whether the frequencies of behaviors found in the selected chick flicks can be applied to the population and prove as a notable part of their perceptions regarding female confidence. Although, the qualitative data could have been more inclusive, with three to five additional film samples to examine in the content analysis. Due to the time constraints of the research process, however, the study was only limited to five chick flick films; future research will benefit from analyzing more films for an understanding of the applicability of the code frequency system to a higher degree. Furthermore, other aspects of this study can be advantageous to future studies, such as the limitations of the sample size. As mentioned earlier, the lack of participants for the experiment led to a decrease in the generalizability of the results, as there was a lack of diverse demographic ranges. With a larger sample size, the results of this research could have much broader applicability and incorporate an abundance of other opinions. Future research could capitalize on the changing nature of chick flicks as well. By analyzing the trend of the makeover trope seen in the chick flicks from this study's focused era (2000-2010), further in the past, and in the present day, researchers can determine whether the chick flick film genre is improving and generating positivity for its young audiences, or the alternative. The larger implications that would stem from the suggested research given and this study involve the physical and mental well-being of young audiences. The trends that begin from films and media, such as the makeover trope, can result in extreme and harmful alterations of young women's looks and behaviors (Jones, 2006).

The paper concludes by arguing that although there is no statistical evidence that the makeover trope influenced the population's perceptions of female confidence, there are qualitative considerations to suggest that it does. This study addressed the significant gaps found in past research of the same field, such as the relation of the makeover trope to female confidence and the time period of 2000-2010. In the future, additional research will be advantageous to address similar ideas, gaps, and limitations found in this study in order to expand society's understanding of common film tropes – like the makeover trope – that can possibly be harming our impressionable minds of tomorrow.

Appendix A: Questions Found in the Pre-Experimental Survey

Open-Ended Questions	Multiple Choice Questions	Linear Scale Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What does “female confidence” mean to you? ● Describe what you think a confident female character should be like in terms of behavior/looks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Do you think watching examples of the makeover trope has influenced the way you've viewed certain people? <p>With answer choices: Yes, No, Maybe, Unsure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a scale from 1 to 10 (1 being “Not at all” and 10 being “Very much so”), how much would you say that characters from any Chick Flicks that you've seen influence your behavior and personal interests?

Appendix B: Questions Found in the Post-Experimental Survey

Control Group (Viewed clips from <i>The Princess Diaries</i> , <i>Legally Blonde</i> , and <i>Mean Girls</i>)	Experimental Group (Viewed clips from <i>The Princess Diaries</i> , <i>Wild Child</i> , and <i>Easy A</i>)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In one word or phrase, describe how Elle's (of <i>Legally Blonde</i>) shift in confidence between the two clips made you feel. ● Briefly describe the differences in confidence level from Cady (of <i>Mean Girls</i>) in the first clip to the second clip. ● How willing would you be to undergo this makeover? (If you were given the opportunity to have this makeover with Paolo and "look like a princess" yourself, would you?) [In response to a clip from <i>The Princess Diaries</i>.] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Poppy's (of <i>Wild Child</i>) transformation is much different from other Chick Flicks with the makeover trope. Do you think her transformation is healthy for her and for viewers to watch? Explain. ● Does Olive's (of <i>Easy A</i>) makeover challenge traditional stereotypes about female confidence or reinforce them? Or both? Briefly explain.

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